

1 **Ecohydrological niche segregation among desert shrubs in a gypsum-calcareous formation,**
2 **north-western Iran**

3

4 **ABSTRACT**

5 **Background:** Xerophilic subshrubs exhibit multiple functional types and frequently show
6 hydrological niche segregation. In the poorly studied Irano-Turanian gypsum deserts, knowledge
7 of the ecohydrological strategies of different plant species is essential to understand community
8 complexity in these vulnerable ecosystems.

9 **Aim:** We studied the ecohydrological strategies of five co-existing subshrubs members of
10 Caryophyllales, ascertaining if their rooting architecture, gypsum affinity or photosynthetic
11 pathway determined their water uptake, and if gypsum crystallisation water could be a relevant
12 water source for plants in different seasons.

13 **Methods:** We conducted soil and xylem sampling for isotope analyses in spring and summer and
14 extracted water by cryogenic vacuum distillation. Oxygen and hydrogen isotope composition were
15 determined and compared with visual representation and Bayesian Mixing Models to determine
16 species ecohydrological strategies.

17 **Results:** Species–season interactions were related to differences in xylem sap isotopic
18 composition. Three basic strategies relying on contrasting the use of free topsoil moisture and deep
19 soil water could be detected and were in part explained by rooting architecture. Plant gypsum
20 affinity and photosynthetic pathways did not have a significant effect on the water sources used
21 by the plants.

22 **Conclusions:** Ecohydrological niche segregation was explained partly by rooting architecture and
23 species-specific traits. Gypsum crystallisation water was not used in summer by the studied
24 species.

25

26 **KEYWORDS:** Caryophyllales, desert subshrubs, gypsum, Iran, niche segregation, stable
27 isotopes, water use.

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33 **Introduction**

34 Arid and semiarid ecosystems are located in regions that are particularly vulnerable to climate
35 change (Hoover et al. 2015; Wertin et al. 2015; Grossiord et al. 2017; Arias et al. 2021). Different
36 forecast climate change scenarios predict an intensification of drought and changes in precipitation
37 patterns (Collins et al. 2013). Temporal and spatial variation in soil water availability is a deter-
38 mining factor for plant distribution and community assembly in these ecosystems (Huxman et al.
39 2005). To cope with scarcity and varying availability of water, plant species from arid ecosystems
40 frequently show hydrological niche segregation (Silvertown 2004; Huxman et al. 2005; Xu et al.
41 2007; Dai et al. 2015; Tiemuerbieke et al. 2018; Wu et al. 2019). The partition of water resources
42 through different mechanisms of water acquisition allows co-existing dryland plant species to ac-
43 cess scant water resources, alleviating competition (Moreno-Gutiérrez et al. 2012; West et al.
44 2012; Silvertown et al. 2015; Brum et al. 2017; Palacio et al. 2017; Iluminati et al. 2022; Querejeta
45 et al. 2022). Determination of water source partitioning among co-occurring plant species and
46 functional types from arid habitats should improve our understanding of the diverse strategies used
47 by plants in these highly adapted and diverse communities. This is essential for accurately project-
48 ing aridification impacts on desert vegetation in the context of climate change.

49 Precipitation pulses are a short-lived water source in desert ecosystems due to fast evap-
50 oration of soil moisture (Ehleringer and Dawson 1992). Thus, precipitation-dependent species are
51 more physiologically stressed during drought periods than those relying on deeper soil water
52 sources or groundwater (Wu et al. 2019). Many dryland plants have developed dimorphic root
53 systems with both shallow and deep roots, which allow them to use water from different soil depths
54 depending on temporal fluctuations in water availability (Bauerle et al. 2008; Prieto et al. 2012;
55 Barbeta et al. 2015). Water from precipitation present in the topsoil after rainfall pulses may be
56 used preferentially during the main growth period, as it favours microbial processes and nutrient
57 uptake by roots (Querejeta et al. 2021). During drought, roots could potentially access deeper soil
58 layers, where water availability is more stable (Ryel et al. 2008, 2010; Fan 2015; Rempe and Die-
59 trich 2018).

60 Plant water use is not only controlled by root functioning, but also by shoot ecophysiological traits
61 (Tiemuerbieke et al. 2018). Xerophyte communities in drylands host multiple functional types,
62 such as different growth forms, and specific traits including leaf and/or stem succulence, leaf
63 reduction or different photosynthetic pathways (e.g., C₃ and C₄) (Rudov et al. 2020; Wertin et al.

64 2015). It has been proposed that C₄ plants have a higher water-use efficiency than C₃ plants
65 (Morgan et al. 2011; Way et al. 2014; Taylor et al. 2014; Helliker and Ehleringer 2002). This
66 assumption is based on the CO₂ concentrating mechanism present in C₄ plants, that allows
67 avoidance of photorespiration even under reduced stomatal conductance and consequently reduces
68 water demand (Ghannoum 2011).

69 Gypsum is an evaporitic mineral frequently present in soils within arid and semiarid landscapes.
70 Endemic-rich ecosystems on gypsum substrate are frequently considered as agricultural badlands,
71 and thus used as dumping places or affected by other negative anthropogenic activities such as
72 mining or urban expansion. The survival of plants in these ecosystems is affected by aridity and
73 harsh edaphic conditions. Gypsum soils have low water retention (Herrero and Porta, 2000), which
74 makes water a critical limiting factor for plants growing on them. However, gypsum holds two
75 water molecules in its crystalline structure (CaSO₄·2H₂O) and can be used as a water source by
76 plants during dry periods (Palacio et al. 2014, 2017; de la Puente et al. 2021). Some plant species
77 have adapted to cope with the physical and chemical restrictions of gypsum soils, behaving as
78 edaphic endemics (gypsophiles) restricted to gypsum soils. In addition, there are gypsum tolerant
79 species (gypsovags) that are not specialised to grow on gypsum soils, but are able to cope with
80 their adverse properties (i.e., low water retention and adverse chemical effects of calcium and
81 sulphate) (Meyer 1986; Cera et al. 2021). In a recent study of a plant community occurring on
82 gypsum in the Iberian Peninsula, it has been shown that crystallisation water was mainly used by
83 shallow rooted species, indicating a critical role of rooting depth to access deep, more stable water
84 sources (de la Puente et al. 2021).

85 Gypsum deserts in the Irano-Turanian floristic region are highly diverse ecosystems, rich
86 in local endemics. The dominant species in these ecosystems are adapted subshrubs that possess
87 different phylogenetic origins, gypsum affinity, photosynthetic pathways, and shoot functional
88 traits, which have been proposed as driving factors for nutrient or water use in other arid ecosys-
89 tems (Palacio et al. 2022; de la Puente et al, 2021; Moreno-Gutierrez et al 2012). These ecosystems
90 are, however, highly understudied both floristically and ecologically. Little is known about the
91 species occurring within these communities and the importance of their functional traits (e.g., suc-
92 culence, photosynthetic pathways, gypsum affinity, root structure) on their ecohydrological mech-
93 anisms of adaptation and their community assemblage. Several of these taxa (e.g., *Anabasis* spp.)
94 are nevertheless of great scientific interest due to their occurrence in the most extreme parts of

95 deserts on gypsum, clay, marl and gravel in Iran. In these edaphically and climatically extreme
96 areas they often comprise the only existing sparse vegetation cover and thus, insights into their
97 ecohydrological mechanisms are of particular interest.

98 The aim of this study was to define the water isotopic composition of xylem sap and the
99 potential water sources used by five dominant woody shrub species coexisting in the arid
100 Aladaghlar hills of north-western Iran and to determine whether the species exhibit segregation of
101 their ecohydrological niches according to different water sources used in spring and summer. We
102 further sought to ascertain whether species, rooting architecture, gypsum affinity and photosyn-
103 thetic pathway were determining factors for differences in water use among species and for their
104 ability to use gypsum crystallisation water. We hypothesised that (1) rooting architecture would
105 be a determinant factor for water use, with species having a deep taproot using deep soil water
106 throughout the year, while species with a dimorphic root system may use water from shallower
107 soil level in spring to deeper level in summer. We further hypothesised that (2) shallow rooted
108 species, independent of gypsum affinity, would use shallow water in spring, but mainly gypsum
109 crystallisation water during the dry season. Finally, regarding the different photosynthetic path-
110 ways of species, we hypothesised that (3) C₄ species with higher leaf-level water use efficiency
111 and root systems relative to C₃ species, should be less dependent on hydrological fluctuations, and
112 thus, continue to rely on the scarce free soil water remaining in the upper soil layers during sum-
113 mer.

114

115 **Materials and methods**

116 *Study area and species*

117 We conducted field sampling in the Aladaghlar hill area of north-western Iran, on the border of
118 the Zanzan and East Azerbaijan provinces (Figure 1, 2A and 2C) (Azizi et al. 2018). The area falls
119 within the Upper Red Formation, which is composed of alternating layers of marl, conglomerate,
120 sandstone and intercalated evaporite layers of crystalline gypsum (Figure 1, 2A and 2C) (Ghorbani
121 2019). The area is located in the Zanzan basin, a remnant of the Tethys Sea of the Early Miocene,
122 which has been shaped by subsequent sedimentation of marine and continental sediments
123 (Rahimpour-Bonab et al. 2007; Alizadeh 2017). The gypsum content of hill slopes varies from 4%
124 to 84% (Table S1). The climate of the region is Irano-Turanian xeric continental (Djamli et al.
125 2011, 2012) with severe drought during summer. Climate data recorded over 55 years at the Zanzan

126 meteorological station, ca. 115 km east of the study area, indicate that total annual precipitation is
127 313 mm and mean annual temperature is 11.5°C (minimum = -7.5°C, maximum = 31.9°C) (Figure
128 1).

129 The harsh climate and the edaphic and topographic characteristics at the study site result in
130 a sparse vegetation, dominated mainly by xerophytic hemicryptophytes and chamaephytes. The
131 area is highly diverse with several endemic species and is understudied with scarce ecological
132 information available in the scientific literature. We selected five dominant woody perennial plant
133 species, *Anabasis calcaria*, *A. eugeniae*, *Caroxylon gemmascens*, *Oreosalsola montana*
134 (Amaranthaceae) and *Atraphaxis suaedifolia* (Polygonaceae) with different affinities to gypsum
135 soils (Figure 2) and different photosynthetic pathways (Table 1; Akhani et al. 2016; Rudov et al.
136 2020; Doostmohammadi et al. 2020). All dominant plant species of this area are succulent and
137 retain large quantities of water in their leaves and/or photosynthetic shoots (Figure 2).

138

139 ***Plant, soil and water sampling***

140 We conducted field sampling for isotope analyses in spring (April and May) 2018 and during the
141 subsequent summer drought in August after a long rainless period. At each sampling date, we
142 harvested the main stems (including the root crown) of five individuals per species. We selected
143 vigorous, medium-sized individuals located at least 5 m apart. We harvested between 6:30 and
144 10:00 a.m., when we expected maximum transpiration rates and low evaporative demand to
145 prevent stem dehydration (Grammatikopoulos et al. 1995; Martín-Gomez et al. 2015). We
146 removed the bark and phloem with a knife to avoid contamination with isotopically enriched
147 phloem water and organic compounds present in living cells and/or in the bark (Ehleringer and
148 Dawson 1992). We also collected two soil samples beneath each plant at two depths (10 and 20
149 cm), excluding roots. In spring, an additional water sample was collected from a temporary creek
150 formed in the valley bottom by a strong rainstorm (14.04.2018) which recharged the groundwater
151 aquifer. This water sample value was used as a representation of the deeper soil water source. All
152 water, stem and soil samples were placed in airtight sealed tubes and immediately frozen in a
153 portable freezer (Allison and Hughes 1983).

154 We observed the root system of at least four individuals per species up to a depth of 40 cm.
155 Additionally, we noted the root system of *Anabasis eugeniae* and *A. calcaria* on eroded steep
156 slopes, where their root systems were exposed. We compared our data with previously published

157 data on root morphology of the species and/or genera investigated (Persson and Baitulin, 1996;
158 Wang et al. 2017; Fet and Atamuradov 1994; Smirnova et al. 1976).

159

160 *Soil gypsum content measurement*

161 Twenty soil samples were collected at a depth of 20 cm from different locations. Samples were
162 left in the laboratory air for several days to completely dry (Jones 2000). Then, samples were
163 processed according to ASTM C702 (1998) and AASHTO T 248 (2014) standard methods and
164 homogenised using a mortar and pestle. The homogenised sample was placed in zip-lock plastic
165 bags. The samples were analysed at the Iranian National Institute of Oceanography and
166 Atmospheric Science. The oven-drying method was used to measure the percentage of gypsum
167 (Porta 1998). In this method, the weight of each empty crucible was measured, then about 2 grams
168 of the homogenised soil samples were transferred into the crucibles, and the crucibles with the soil
169 were weighed again. Gypsum mineral was added to one of the crucibles as a control. The samples
170 were placed in an oven at a temperature of 50 °C for at least 4 h. After this period, the samples
171 were weighed again. In the next step, the crucibles were placed in an oven at a temperature of 105
172 °C for at least 4 h, and after this time, they were weighed again.

173

174 *Water extraction*

175 We extracted xylem and soil water using a modified cryogenic vacuum distillation (Ehleringer and
176 Dawson 1992) as in Palacio et al. (2014). Xylem water was extracted at CEBAS-CSIC (Murcia,
177 Spain) using cryogenic vacuum distillation at 100 °C and 1.3 Pa vacuum pressure for 2 h (Querejeta
178 et al. 2021). Soil samples were extracted at the laboratory of the Instituto Pirenaico de Ecología
179 (IPE-CSIC, Zaragoza, Spain). Sample tubes were placed in a heated silicone oil bath, and
180 connected with Ultra-Torr unions (Swagelok Company, Solon, OH, USA) to a vacuum system (ca.
181 1 Pa) including U-shaped water traps in series that were cooled with liquid nitrogen. After an
182 extraction time of 90 min (West 2006; Meissner 2014), captured water was transferred into screw-
183 capped 2-ml vials and stored at 4 °C until isotope analysis. Soil samples were distilled in two steps:
184 first at 35 °C and then at 130 °C to separate free and gypsum crystallisation water while ensuring
185 an almost complete dehydration of gypsum (Freyer and Voigt 2003; Palacio et al. 2014). When
186 necessary, between the first and second distillation of soil samples, we kept sample tubes in a

187 desiccator with silica gel to avoid any re-hydration with ambient moisture, which could
188 contaminate the water extracted in the second step.

189

190 *Stable isotope analyses*

191 The use of water stable isotopes (^2H and ^{18}O) as natural tracers to understand water up-
192 take by plants has been reported extensively in plant ecology (Dawson et al. 2002). A vertical
193 gradient in the isotopic composition of soil water is commonly found in arid ecosystems, where
194 the upper soil areas are enriched in the heavier isotopes because of more pronounced evaporative
195 isotopic fractionation (Allison and Hughes 1983; Orłowski et al. 2013).

196 We determined oxygen and hydrogen isotope composition ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) using Isotope Ratio Mass
197 Spectrometers (IRMS) at the Center for Stable Isotope Biogeochemistry (CSIB) of the University
198 of California at Berkeley (USA). $\delta^2\text{H}$ was determined by the dual inlet method, using a hot
199 chromium reactor unit (H/DeviceTM, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), coupled to
200 a Thermo Delta Plus XL mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific), using multiple standards
201 in every run, and correcting for drifts using two internal standards with different isotope ratios.
202 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ was determined by the equilibration method, using a Thermo Gas Bench II interface, coupled
203 to a Thermo Delta Plus XL mass spectrometer (Bremen, Germany). Briefly, ca. 20 μL of water
204 were pipetted into 10 mL glass vials (Exetainer®, Labco Ltd., UK) and sealed. The vials were
205 purged with 0.2% CO_2 in helium and equilibrated at room temperature for 48 hours. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
206 value of CO_2 was then determined by IRMS. Long-term external precision is ± 0.60 ‰ and ± 0.12
207 ‰ for $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, respectively.

208

209 *Statistical analyses*

210 We made all statistical analyses in R 4.0.0 (R Core Team, 2020). We used *ggplot2* (Wickham
211 2016) to visualise xylem sap isotopic composition and soil water at different sampling dates, the
212 $\delta^2\text{H}$ – $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ plot space and contributions of the water sources to plants. To account for seasonal
213 changes (April–August) in isotopic composition in xylem water of the five species and in the water
214 sources (free and crystallisation water), we used GLMs separately for each species and water
215 source type (including season as a fixed factor) with the *lm* function of the *nlme* package (v3.1-
216 152; Pinheiro et al., 2021). Differences among study species (fixed factor) and sampling dates
217 (fixed factor) in xylem water isotopic composition ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) were evaluated using the *lmer*

218 function, which uses the Maximum Likelihood estimation. Similarly, the effects of season, rooting
219 architecture, gypsum affinity, photosynthetic pathway and their interaction with the season of
220 sampling on the xylem isotopic composition of the species were also checked with the *lmer*
221 function. In this case, rooting architecture, gypsum affinity, photosynthetic pathway and season
222 were considered as fixed factors, whereas species and plant family nested within species were
223 included as random terms to account for potential phylogenetic effects. When the effect of the
224 factor was significant on the xylem sap isotopic composition, groups were detected using a post-
225 hoc Tukey test. Over- and under-dispersion of model residuals were checked using the
226 *simulateResiduals* function in *DHARMA* package v.0.3.1 (Hartig 2021).

227 The relative contribution of different sources to the xylem water of plants was estimated
228 using Bayesian Mixing Models for stable isotope data, using the package *MixSIAR* (Stock et al.
229 2018). The package, originally developed for dietary studies, estimates the relative contribution of
230 alternative preys (sources) to a given consumer (mixture), considering the multidimensional space
231 formed by two or more biotracers (e.g., stable isotope composition) in the sources and the
232 consumers. We used the isotopic values ($\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) of xylem water (consumer) in each
233 individual sample (i.e., every single replicate of all the species) as inputs for the model. The mean
234 and standard deviation (per species) for each alternative soil source (free and crystallisation water,
235 at 10 cm and 20 cm soil depth collected beneath each individual plant), and the water value of the
236 creek, representing deep soil water, were considered as inputs for the sources. For the creek water
237 collected in spring, only one replicate sample was available, so we had the same value for all plant
238 species and replicates. As a conservative approximation of the standard deviation for this source,
239 we choose the mean of the standard deviation of the other two free water sources. Alternatively,
240 we also tested the models using the analytical error, as the only measured uncertainty for this
241 source (0.4 for $\delta^2\text{H}$ and 0.1 for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$; Supplementary Materials, Methods S2). These two alternative
242 models did not show noticeable differences in the trends of water sources used by study species.

243 To simplify the interpretation of the Bayesian Mixing Model, the output was combined *a*
244 *posteriori* through the addition of the estimated contributions of each source into three simplified
245 sources. First, crystal water (i.e., gypsum crystallisation water from the soil) that was calculated
246 by adding the contributions to the xylem of plants from crystallisation water at the two depths
247 initially considered (10 and 20 cm). Second, free water (i.e., free water in the shallow soil), was

248 calculated by adding the contribution to the xylem from the free water at 10 and 20 cm. Third,
249 deep soil free water (i.e., free water in the deep soil) was kept unmodified.

250

251 **Results**

252 ***Water sources and species xylem sap isotopic composition***

253 The oxygen isotopic composition of gypsum crystallization water was stable in both seasons, but
254 in August it was less enriched in ^2H . Free soil water changed its $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ composition among
255 sampled months (Figure 3, Table S3). We found differences in $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of xylem sap between
256 spring and summer for *Anabasis calcaria* and *A. eugeniae*, but only in $\delta^2\text{H}$ for *Atraphaxis*
257 *suaedifolia* (Figure 3, Table S3).

258 Species, season and their interaction were all significant factors explaining differences in xylem
259 sap isotopic composition ($\delta^2\text{H}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$), except for seasonal variation in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (Table 2).
260 Contrastingly, neither plant rooting architecture, gypsum affinity nor photosynthetic pathway had
261 a significant effect on the isotopic composition of the xylem water of plants (Table 2). However,
262 we observed a marginally significant interaction between species gypsum affinity and sampling
263 month for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the xylem (Table 2) though a post-hoc Tukey test did not separate clear groups.
264

265 ***Contribution of different water sources to the xylem water of plants***

266 The analysis of the isotopic values ($\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) of xylem sap and water sources (Figure 4)
267 showed that crystallisation water isotope values were the most distant from those of xylem sap in
268 both April and August. The deep soil water source was less exposed to evaporation and therefore
269 showed less evaporatively enriched isotopic values than shallower free soil water (Figure 4).
270 Species could be separated according to their xylem sap isotopic composition with *Aanabasis*
271 *calcaria* (DT), *Atraphaxis suaedifolia* (T) and *Caroxylon gemmascens* (S) exhibiting very similar
272 compositions in April, close to that of shallow free water at 10 cm depth. In contrast, *Anabasis*
273 *eugeniae* (DT) and, especially, *Oreosalsola montana* (T), had xylem sap isotopic values that were
274 less enriched and similar to those of deeper free water. These relationships changed in August,
275 with *C. gemmascens* (S) and *A. eugeniae* (DT) having a relatively similar isotopic composition in
276 their xylem sap, close to that of shallow free water, whereas the three other species, and especially
277 *A. calcaria* (DT) and *O. montana* (T), had compositions close to that of deep free water (Figure
278 4).

279 Bayesian Mixing Model estimation of the most likely sources of water used by the species
280 indicated some notable differences between them (Figure 5, Table 3, Table S4). *Oreosalsola*
281 *montana* used deep soil water as its main water source in both seasons, whereas the other species,
282 and especially *A. eugeniae* and *C. gemmascens*, used free water available from the upper layers of
283 the soil profile as their main water source in spring. In summer, *A. eugeniae* and *C. gemmascens*
284 were least dependent on deep soil water, whereas the three other species were heavily dependent
285 on this water source (Figure 5, Table 3, Table S4). The model confirmed that crystallisation water
286 from gypsum was a less important water source for each of the species (Figure 5), though in April
287 it contributed 33% and 25% to the water used by *A. suaedifolia* and *C. gemmascens*, respectively
288 (Figure 5, Table 3, Table S4).

289

290

291 **Discussion**

292

293 Our results revealed the different water sources used by five dominant subshrub species in the
294 poorly studied gypsum-rich Aladaghar hills, north-western Iran, and contribute to an
295 understanding of how such differences might be important to niche segregation and the coexistence
296 of these species under the conditions of extreme aridity and harsh soil conditions they are subject
297 to.

298 According to our results, the species showed differences in their vertical ecohydrological niches,
299 resulting in different water uptake patterns. Ecohydrological niche segregation has been observed
300 in other desert regions of the world, such as in the Gurbantunggut Desert of China (Wu et al. 2013;
301 Timuerbieke et al. 2018), the Glen Canyon in Utah, North America (Ehleringer et al. 1991) and
302 the Namib Desert in Africa (Schachtschneider, 2010). In these regions, the divergent rooting
303 depths of coexisting species were shown to play an important role in water use segregation, thereby
304 avoiding or minimising interspecific competition for scarce water during drought (Dawson and
305 Pate 1996). In the present study we hypothesised that rooting depth might also be a significant
306 factor affecting water source uptake of species and their ecohydrological niche segregation, and
307 this prediction was fulfilled for three of the five species studied. *Oreosalsola montana*, whose root
308 system consists of a deep taproot, was found to dependent on deep soil water in both spring (April)
309 and summer (August). *Caroxylon gemmascens*, with a shallow root system, used high quantities

310 of superficial water in both of these seasons. On the other hand, *A. calcarea*, with a dimorphic root
311 system described also in other *Anabasis* species (Persson and Baitulin 1996), shifted from using
312 preferentially shallow water in spring to mainly deep soil water during summer drought. Such a
313 shift to the use of deeper water sources during summer is in accordance with previous findings
314 from studies in other arid ecosystems. Such shifts have been suggested to serve as a strategy to
315 maximise nutrient uptake during the wet spring season, while securing access to deeper and more
316 reliable and abundant water sources during the dry summer when evaporative demand is high
317 (Querejeta et al. 2021).

318 Contrary to our hypothesis, however, *Anabasis eugeniae*, which also has a dimorphic root system,
319 used preferentially water from the shallow topsoil layer in both spring and summer, potentially
320 indicating a primary anchoring function of its taproot. *A. suaedifolia*, which has only a long taproot
321 (Persson and Baitulin 1996; Wang et al. 2017), was nonetheless also able to use shallow topsoil
322 water in spring. This period coincides with generative shoot formation and flowering in *Atraphaxis*
323 spp. and thus may require additional nutrient uptake from the nutrient-rich surface soil (Kostina
324 and Yurtseva 2021). These results are intriguing, since dimorphic roots have not been recorded for
325 *A. suaedifolia* in the field. More observations on the root system of this species should be made to
326 ascertain its rooting system in detail.

327 Our hypothesis about the potential use of crystallisation water held in gypsum by shallow
328 rooted species was not supported by our results. We found that among the potential water sources
329 available to plants, the isotopic composition of gypsum crystallisation water was the most distant
330 and dissimilar from the isotopic composition of plant xylem water in all the species (Figure 4), and
331 Bayesian Mixing Models analysis showed crystallisation water as the least likely water source
332 used by plants. Although it is not possible to completely rule out crystallisation water as a minor
333 water source for some of the species studied, the low probability of its use, compared to what has
334 been reported for other ecosystems (e.g., de la Puente et al 2022), suggests that it is not an
335 important water source in this ecosystem. Recent studies have shown that coexisting plants use
336 different water sources depending on their rooting depth and position along gypsum hills (Palacio
337 et al. 2017; de la Puente et al. 2021). Shallow-rooted plants growing on soils with high gypsum
338 content showed a widespread use of gypsum crystalline water during summer, while deep-rooted
339 plants tended to use free soil water from deep soil layers (de la Puente et al. 2021). Previous studies
340 reporting substantial use of gypsum crystallisation water were conducted in gypsum hills where

341 gypsum content in the soil was homogeneous and accounted for more than 60% (Palacio et al.
342 2017; de la Puente et al. 2021). However, soils beneath the plants in our ecosystem studied varied
343 from ca. 91% gypsum content to 4% sometimes even on the same slope (Table S1), suggesting
344 that the highly spatially variable gypsum content of the soil may be a limitation to its use as a water
345 source. It is, hence, probable that the presence of gypsum in the rhizosphere of many or all of our
346 study plants was minimal. Alternatively, the availability of other potential free soil water sources
347 was sufficient to supply plants with water even during the dry summer.

348 In relation to the isotopic composition of the deep water source considered in our study,
349 we propose that, in future studies, more rigorous sampling is employed with more detailed
350 characterisation of soil water isotopic composition at different depths of the soil profile. We
351 considered a generic deep soil water pool (using creek water as a proxy for groundwater), without
352 specifying an exact depth, to refer to water that is less evaporated and shows no evidence of
353 evaporative isotopic enrichment in the heavier isotopes in this seasonally dry area (Allison and
354 Hughes 1983; but see Sánchez-Martín et al, 2021; Ding et al. 2021). Consequently, our results
355 should be taken as an approximation of the proportions of water uptake from different depths in
356 the different seasons; and not as an exact quantification of the water sources taken up by the plant
357 species.

358 The traditional assumption of absence of isotopic fractionation during water uptake has
359 been questioned in some studies (Ellsworth and Williams 2007; Barbeta et al. 2020), which found
360 that $\delta^2\text{H}$ of xylem water can be more depleted than the water source considered. However, in our
361 study we observed that xylem sap $\delta^2\text{H}$ values were not more negative than those of the water
362 sources available to plants as observed in those cited previous works. This suggests that the $\delta^2\text{H}$
363 of xylem water accurately reflected the $\delta^2\text{H}$ of the soil water sources in our study, thereby
364 facilitating the data analysis with Bayesian Mixing models using both water isotopes.

365 Our results further showed that water niche segregation strategies are not directly related
366 to the photosynthetic pathway in the five desert species analysed. For example, *A. calcarea* (C_4)
367 shifted to deep soil water sources during the period of summer drought, similarly to the C_3 species
368 *A. suaedifolia*. On the other hand, we could explain the use of shallower and scarce free water by
369 *A. eugeniae* and *C. gemmascens* by their photosynthetic pathway, both species are highly drought
370 tolerant C_4 plants, so their photosynthetic pathway adapted to warm and dry climatic conditions
371 may contribute to a higher water-use efficiency, decreasing their reliance on deep water.

372 Nevertheless, we also observed that the relative of *A. eugeniae*, *A. calcarea*, also C₄, used a large
373 proportion of deep water in summer. Similar patterns have been described in plants from other
374 desert ecosystems. For example, ecohydrological niche segregation has been observed between
375 the closely related C₄ desert shrubs *Haloxylon ammodendron* and *H. persicum* (Dai et al. 2015,
376 Wu et al. 2019). Although these two *Haloxylon* species share common habitats (sand deserts) and
377 have comparable extensive root systems, *H. ammodendron* switches from shallow water use to
378 groundwater use during the hot dry season, while *H. persicum* continues to depend on free topsoil
379 water during the entire dry season (Dai et al. 2015, Wu et al. 2019). Furthermore, deep-rooting C₃
380 desert shrubs, such as *Tamarix* species, have been shown to rely on deep soil water as the main
381 water source during the whole year, similarly to *O. montana*, while shallow-rooting species, such
382 as *Nitraria tangutorum* (C₃), *Reaumuria songarica* (C₃) and *Calligonum leucocladum* (C₄),
383 continue to rely largely on the scarce free soil water pool even during dry periods (Xu and Li 2006;
384 Xu et al. 2007; Wu et al. 2014; Tiemuerbieke et al. 2018), similar to our findings for *C.*
385 *gemmascens* and *A. eugeniae*.

386 The reason for the differences in water source use between the two *Anabasis* species and
387 the most important functional traits related to them still need further attention, but studies on the
388 dimorphic root systems of related *Anabasis* species point to their ability to rely on several
389 complementary water sources. In contrast to C₄ monocots, C₄ eudicots typical for the Irano-
390 Turanian deserts, have a higher diversity of functional traits and ecophysiological adaptations to
391 their environment. Thus, differences in ecohydrological strategies of phylogenetically close taxa
392 may, at least partly, be related to the variety of adaptations and functional traits they present
393 (Akhani 2006; Cayssials and Rodriguez 2013; Matinzadeh et al. 2019; Rudov et al. 2020). In our
394 case, the two *Anabasis* species differ in their shoot morphology, *A. eugeniae* being a leaf-succulent
395 subshrub, while *A. calcarea* is a caudex forming stem-succulent. The genus *Anabasis* is known to
396 include some of the most extremophilic desert species, growing in exceptionally dry habitats and
397 forming species-poor vegetation types (Lauterbach et al. 2019). It presents a variety of ecotypes,
398 functional traits and growth forms, that include annuals, and perennial leaf and stem succulents,
399 which may affect ecohydrological strategies of each species (Rudov et al. 2020).

400

401 **Conclusions**

402 The five species studied showed distinct ecohydrological niche segregation, using different pro-
403 portions of free water acquired from different soil depths. Although growing on a gypsum-rich
404 substrate in certain patches of soil, these species did not rely on gypsum crystallisation water as a
405 main water source during the summer drought. Neither gypsum affinity nor photosynthetic path-
406 way had any significant effect on the water sources used by the different coexisting species. These
407 xerophytic species revealed three basic strategies of water use. First, deep soil water was the main
408 source throughout the growing season by *O. montana*. Second, a drastic shift from topsoil water
409 in April to deep soil water in August by *A. calcarea* and *A. suaedifolia*. Third, moderate variation
410 in use of more topsoil water in April to more deep water in August by *A. eugeniae* and *C. gem-*
411 *mascens*. Rooting architecture was an explanatory factor for the water sources used for *O. mon-*
412 *tana*, *A. calcarea* and *C. gemmascens*.

413

414

415 **Disclosure statement**

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417

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705 rain pulse events. *Plant Soil.* 285(1):5–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-005-5108-9>

707 **Table 1.** Plant species included in the study with indication of their growth form, plant size, type
 708 of root system, affinity for gypsum soils and taxonomic family, north-western Aladaglar Hills,
 709 Iran. SSS, stem succulent subshrub; LSS, leaf succulent subshrub; DT, long taproot with the
 710 presence of a dimorphic root system; T, long taproot; S, shallow root system (less than 1 m depth);
 711 GV, gypsog; GP, gypsophile.

Id.	Species	Growth form & plant size	Root system	Gypsum affinity	Photo-syntetic type	Family
An.ca	<i>Anabasis calcarea</i> (Charif & Aellen) Bokhari & Wendelbo	SSS 20-40 cm	DT (1)	GV	C ₄	Amaranthaceae
An.eu	<i>Anabasis eugeniae</i> Iljin	LSS 20 cm	DT (1)	GP	C ₄	Amaranthaceae
At.su	<i>Atraphaxis suaedifolia</i> Jaub & Spach	LSS 40 cm	T (1, 2)	GP	C ₃	Polygonaceae
Ca.ge	<i>Caroxylon gemmascens</i> (Pall.) Tzvelev	LSS 20-40 cm	S (3, 4)	GV	C ₄	Amaranthaceae
Or.mo	<i>Oreosalsola montana</i> (Litv) Akhani.	LSS 50 cm	T (5)	GV	C ₃	Amaranthaceae

712 References: (1) Persson & Baitulin, 1996; (2) Wang et al. 2017; (3) Fet and Atamuradov 1994; (4)
 713 Rudov – unpublished data; (5) Smirnova et al. 1976.

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715

716 **Table 2.** Maximum likelihood (*lmer* function) mixed models analysing differences in the isotopic
717 composition of the xylem sap among species and seasons, and among three fixed factors
718 (gypsophily, photosynthetic pathway and rooting architecture) and their interaction with season,
719 north-western Aladaghlar Hills, Iran. Observed rooting architecture of the species included three
720 levels: DT, S, T (see Table 1), the affinity for gypsum soils (gypsophily) had two levels: gypsovag
721 and gypsophile, and the photosynthetic pathway of the species had two levels: C₃ and C₄. F-ratios
722 and *P*-values are shown. Significant effects are highlighted in bold type.

723

	$\delta^2\text{H}$ (‰)		$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰)	
	<i>F</i> -ratio	<i>P</i> -value	<i>F</i> -ratio	<i>P</i> -value
Species	6.19	< 0.001	7.29	< 0.001
Season	9.84	0.004	0.23	0.637
Species : Season	10.71	< 0.001	7.44	< 0.001
Gypsophily	0.06	0.814	0.16	0.724
Gypsophily : Season	1.41	0.244	4.40	0.044
Photosynthetic pathway	0.19	0.701	0.21	0.678
Photosynthetic pathway : Season	0.91	0.348	1.15	0.291
Rooting depth architecture	0.59	0.665	0.99	0.550
Rooting depth architecture : Season	1.01	0.377	0.61	0.547

724

725

726

727 **Table 3.** Results of Bayesian Mixing Models result shown as showing the percentage of estimated
 728 contribution of the three potential water sources, combined from the initial five potential sources
 729 (see materials and methods for further details), in the xylem sap of the subshrub species, north-
 730 western Aladaghlar Hills, Iran.

731

Season	Species	Crystallization		
		Crystallisation water (%)	Shallow free water (%)	Deep free water (%)
SPRING- Spring	<i>Oreosalsola montana</i>	11.66	29.69	58.65
	<i>Caroxylon gemmascens</i>	25.69	45.21	29.11
	<i>Atraphaxis suaedifolia</i>	33.05	39.46	27.49
	<i>Anabasis eugeniae</i>	10.86	53.44	35.69
	<i>Anabasis calcarea</i>	24.22	42.2	33.57
SUM- MER- Summer	<i>Oreosalsola montana</i>	9.3	17.92	72.78
	<i>Caroxylon gemmascens</i>	21.73	31.51	46.76
	<i>Atraphaxis suaedifolia</i>	6.49	25.45	68.05
	<i>Anabasis eugeniae</i>	23.82	37.69	38.49
	<i>Anabasis calcarea</i>	8.94	16.14	74.93

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734

735 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

736

737 **Figure 1.** Location of the sampling sites, north-western Aladaghlar Hills, study area in NW Iran
738 and Sampling sites. Blue droplets dots denote the location of water samples, and the transparent
739 green rectangles denote the areas where plant samples were collected. The lower left panel is the
740 climate diagram based on long long-term climate data collected at major meteorological stations
741 in the region.

742

743 **Figure 2.** Habitat and plant species studied for ecohydrological niche segregation in a gypsium-
744 calcareous habitat, north-western Aladaghlar Hills, Iran in NW Iran. A. Gypsum-calcareous hills
745 with showing *Anabasis eugeniae* in foreground and *A. calcarea* in background, inset shows close-
746 up of a fruiting branch of *A. eugeniae* on a gypsum outcrop; B. *Anabasis calcarea*; C. Marl hill
747 with *Caroxylon gemmascens*, *Oreosalsola montana* and *Atraphaxis suaedifolia*; D. Habit and
748 close close-up of a fruiting branch of *Caroxylon gemmascens*; E. Habit and close up of a fruiting
749 branch of *Oreosalsola montana*; F. Habit and flowering branch of *Atraphaxis suaedifolia*
750 (Photographic credit: by Hossein Akhani).

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753

754 **Figure 3.** $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of the xylem sap of the plant species and soil in both months (April
755 and August), north-western Aladaghlar Hills, Iran. Labels for plant species correspond to *Anabasis*
756 *calcareea* (Aca), *Anabasis eugeniae* (Aeu), *Atraphaxis suaedifolia* (Asu), *Caroxylon gemmascens*
757 (Cage) and *Oreosalsola montana* (Omo). The asterisks (*, $P<0.05$) in the labels indicate
758 statistically significate changes differences in isotopic composition. of the stable isotopes in the
759 xylem sap of the species and in the free and crystallization water among seasons indicated in the
760 linear mixing model (nlme package)

761

762 **Figure 4.** Xylem sap isotopic composition of the species grouped by their gypsum affinity and
763 photosynthetic pathway for both seasons. (These grouping factors did not show any significant
764 influence on the xylem sap isotopic composition of the subshrub species, see Table 1)

765

766 **Figure 5.** Plots showing the $\delta^2\text{H}$ (‰) and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰) composition of the different sources of water
767 and water xylem sap of the five different species and the global meteoric water line (GMWL) in
768 spring and summer, north-western Aladaghlar Hills, Iran. Values are means \pm plus SD. The colour
769 in of the sources symbols are for indicates the depth of the source: black= , 10 cm depth,; grey=,
770 20 cm depth.

771

772 **Figure 6.** Results from Bayesian stable isotope mixing models showing the estimated contribution
773 of different water sources to the xylem water of the five plant species from community studied in
774 April and in August, north-western Aladaghlar Hills, Iran. The sources named “Crystal” and
775 “Free” included gypsum crystallization crystallisation water and free water, respectively, sampled
776 at two different depths: 10 and 20 cm underneath the plants; “Deep soil water” represented
777 represents deeper water.

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780 Fig. 1

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783 Fig. 2

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795 Fig. 6.

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